

₹ 250/-

ITIHAS

The Journal of Indian Management

Volume : 5

Issue : 3

July - September 2015

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• **ISSN 2249-7803**

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ITIHAS The Journal of Indian Management

H.No. 16-11-310/2/3/C, Saleem Nagar Colony,
Moosarambagh, Hyderabad - 500 036.

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Corporate Social Responsibility: A Case Study of two Indian Companies for the Inclusive Development

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ABSTRACT

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is becoming a progressively more important event of companies internationally and domestically. The companies have increasingly recognized the benefits of spending towards CSR activities in their various plant locations. CSR activities are now being carried out across the globe. In this paper the researcher has made an attempt to understand the CSR in enriching with particular reference to three emerging companies viz. (a) Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Ltd; and (b) Cairn India Ltd in India.

Keywords : Corporate Social Responsibility, Livelihood, Education, Healthcare.

Introduction

CSR has come a long path way in Indian corporate sector. From a symbolic way of approach to impact intervention. In the present social situations of India, it was so difficult for a single body to carry about change as the scale was massive. Corporate have the strategic thinking, expertise, human resource and money to make easy wide social change. Effective association needs among the Indian corporate sector, government and the NGOs was placed good in India's CSR service on a rapid way. India's poor not only misplace their source of income at the time of illness, but also go throughout great adversity to get better.

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is another name for corporate conscience and responsible business. It involves a business model into which the concept of corporate self-regulation has a natural in the country. Social responsibility of corporate has a self-governing means ensuring that any business organization abides by with the spirit of the law, maintains ethical standards and observes domestic and international standards. Thus, the role of the corporate in guiding the culture of the society cannot survive unnoticed. It looks that in the in progress period of the capitalism overpowering the socialist ideologies; the corporate will dominate and guide other social-cultural institution of the society.

In an increasingly conscience-focused marketplace of the 21st century the more demand for extra moral

business functions and events increasing. Simultaneously, pressure is applied on Indian corporate sector to improve business ethics through new public initiatives. Business ethics can be both a normative and explanatory order. Firms practice along with occupation specialization the ground has mainly normative. The range and quantity of business is perceived to be at odds with non-economic social values. Today major corporate houses lay emphasis on commitment to promoting non-economic social values under a variety of headings- social responsibility being one of them. In some cases, corporations have re-branded their core values in the light of business ethical considerations.

Review of Literature

The massive rise in the literature, in modern years, which arrangement with CSR and associated concepts, CSR is still today impossible to simply describe. First, it is due to the information that CSR concept among a comparatively open application convention (Matten and Moon, 2008; Moon et al., 2005; Vogel, 2005). Second, CSR is a type of umbrella, which goes above, or is fitting synonymous by other business-community relations concepts (Matten and Moon, 2008; Matten and Crane, 2005). Lastly, CSR is still especially energetic phenomenon (Matten and Moon, 2008; Asongu, 2007; Carroll, 1999). Therefore nearby a large definitions, which attempt to confine the CSR concept. Content varies and is also frequently possible to see

from them, whether acquired in the government sector, the academics sphere, the commercial sector, for example, presented different definitions.

According to European Commission, (2001) CSR is a model whereby corporate incorporate environmental and social concerns in their functions and in their communication with their stakeholders on a voluntarily. Matten and Moon, (2008) at the heart of CSR it is the concept that it replicate the social vital role and the social consequences of corporate achievement.

Carroll (1991) designed and developed CSR model on the basis of argument on 4 foundation, According to his CSR thinking model is made up of the subsequent mechanism in a below order; (i) be profitable-economic responsibility; (ii) obey the law-legal responsibility; (iii) be ethical- ethical responsibility and (iv) be a good international corporate citizen-philanthropic responsibility. Even though the typology classiness of Carrolls, it is inclined to assume a coherent and consistent internal control logic running throughout the different components of CSR. The typology also is inclined to play down the inherent tensions and tradeoffs that exist among these mechanisms.

Carroll's CSR Pyramid

Source: Carroll, (1991)

According to coherent of Carroll's model directly and indirectly, a widespread objective in profit oriented-these could be tangible branding and intangible that reputation is visible, and though still it emphasize the vital objective of companies towards maximization of profit (Urmela, 2012, and Kiran and Sharma 2013).

Objectives of the Study

- (i) To elicit the role of various corporate social responsibility(CSR) practices in Indian companies;

Methodology of the Study

Comprehensive review of literature regarding the concepts and topic has been done. The present study was done with the main objectives of understanding and practices of 2 emerging companies CSR activities of Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Ltd., and Cairn India Ltd.. The study is mainly based on secondary sources of information collected from sustainable reports and website of the companies.

(A) Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Ltd.

Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Ltd is a pharmaceutical company based in Hyderabad, Telangana, India. The corporate was found by Anji Reddy, who had before worked in the mentor institute Indian Drugs and Pharmaceuticals Ltd, Hyderabad, India. Dr. Reddy's produces and markets a broad variety of pharmaceuticals in India and abroad. The company has over 190 medications, 60 active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) for drug produce, critical care, diagnostic kits, and biotechnology goods.

CSR activities of Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Ltd.

Strengthening education, livelihood formation, Dr. Reddy's foundation acts as a catalyst of change that develops, fosters, and promotes initiatives at individual group and managerial levels to accomplish sustainable development. Sustainable development cannot occur until people are empowered to support themselves and hence the foundation focuses on livelihood creation and education through it's a variety of livelihood advancement business schools and through it's a lot of innovative activities in the School Education campus.

Labs Partnerships Initiated

Michael & Susan Dell Foundation in association with this Foundation, DRF has take on to supply sustainable livelihood exercise to 6000 youth from slum pockets that are individual replace to resettlement areas on the outer edge of the Delhi's National Capital Region. MP Rural Livelihood's scheme under this project, DRF has recognized LABS centers in the Annupur , Sheopur, Dhar and Shadole districts of Madhya Pradesh.

(a) New Livelihood Options offered

Construction to tie together the incredible livelihood options thrown up by the Indian fast-growing infrastructure sector, DRF and national academy of construction have combined to jointly conduct training programs in construction operation such as electrical (home wiring), masonry, general works supervisor, sanitation and plumbing. The first training batches have been commenced at a few LABS centers in AP. Direct Sales DRF and HUL have jointly developed direct sales training programs to equip LABS aspirants in a variety of aspects of straight promotion. This meticulous program was beginning in phases in different LABS centers crosswise India. In partnership with the government of India, various state governments, other NGOs and the private sector, DRF has set up labs across India. A total of 42,064 livelihoods were generated in 2011-12 in the various states of India.

(i) Promoting Micro Entrepreneurs

Through the companies LABS program have been developed innovative models for self-employment throughout micro entrepreneurship programs, which nurture adults and youth for entrepreneurship through development of skills, market linkages and development of business plan. Below the Aarogya program, over 75 mobile food vendors in Karimnagar, Andra Pradesh have been helped in developing their corporate businesses. The program was been scaled up to include 200 beneficiary in a only some Hyderabad municipalities. DRF has been locate eight Yuva youth education centers in Hyderabad and RR Districts, which run two bridge plans for disadvantaged youth, to allow them to obtain side entry into the conventional education system. Underneath the Sayodya program, 25 partly disabled youth in RR District (AP) have been assisted in earning their livelihoods during corn trade in specially planned kiosks. The activities was been extended to include 1000 beneficiary, in relationship with DRDA, Andra Pradesh. In the year 2007, 50 youth were skilled under phase II

program. Some of them have created an SHG and set up a refreshment shops in an office complex in Hyderabad.

(ii) Rashtra Chenetha Jana Samakhya

DRF signed a MoU with Rashtra Chenetha Jana Samakhya, a handloom weavers' union based at Chirala (AP), under which DRF will offered funding for the development of a loom that will decrease the strain on a weaver. The multi national Institute of Information Technology, Hyderabad, has been co-opted as the technological associate in the project.

(b) Spreading smiles through Education

Using schools as community learning resource centres, DRF strives to reduce school drop-out rates by developing local knowledge, skills and leadership. Adopting 72 government schools in Balanagar Mandal (RR District) and Hyderabad-Secunderabad, DRF has launched several innovative initiatives in curriculum development, teacher training and community involvement.

(i) Yuva Youth Learning Centers

DRF has set up 8 yuva youth education centers in Hyderabad and RR Districts, which run two bridge programs for deprived youth, to permit them to find side entry into the conventional education system. Adolescent Bridge Courses (ABCs) trainer 250-500 school dropouts students every year to appear for the Class 10 Board examinations of the Government of Andra Pradesh. 287 students appeared for the Class 10 exams that were held in March and April 2008.

Under the included Learning program (ILP), never been- to-school adolescents, adolescent girls and child labor working as home help are put throughout a foundation Course in basic Telugu, English, Math, environmental sciences and health education. They are also ready for Classes 7th to 9th under the AP open school society. In this year, 213 pupils are appearing for the open school examination. The centers tender career guidance, soft skills, spoken English and computer education, thereby allowing the youth to make

choices about their bright future. This also minimizes chances of the girls being obliged into premature marriage. Above 250, such girls have been withdrawn from home labour and admit to these Centers.

(ii) ALTIUS, the Advancement school

DRF has set upped ALTIUS, an advancement school that serves as a phase for post graduates, graduates and diploma holders to way in a variety of opportunities of career development by as long as them with necessary employment skills. It kindhearted training in call center operations, accountancy packages and medical transcription, in adding to communicative language skills, spoken English and computer fundamental training. Below the government maintained SSA and DRF also carry out a housing bridge course for drop out from school and those engaged in child labor, DRFHE'S 1 year post-graduate course in health care management has placed 212 pupils in hospitals, pharma companies and clinics.

(iii) Residential Bridge Courses

Under the central government-supported Sarva Siksha Abhiyan(SSA), DRF also conducted a residential bridge course for out of- school pupils and those occupied in child labour. 67 girls and 101 boys have been mainstreamed into regular education and housed in social welfare hostels. To make sure their sustained education, DRF has started a hostel support programs, which consists of a dedicated hostel tutors and volunteer to coach them to improve their educational standards.

(iv) Schedule Tribal School Program (STSP)

In VR Puram Mandal, Khammam District, Andra Pradesh, DRF was worked with 33 government schools in areas inhabited by Konda and Koya schedule tribes. After holding several discussions and workshops with teachers, elders and youth in the Mandal, DRF has published several books including stories, primers, riddles and poems in their languages, using the Telugu play. Meant for students who have passed the Class 10 Board Examination Kallam anji reddy professional junior college offers 2 years professional courses. The

ISSN No.2249-7803
ISS

(v) Pudami Primary Schools

In the year 2007 DRF started 14 pudami english primaries in Hyderabad. Set up in neighborhoods containing huge populations of poor urban, these English medium primaries teach English, Environmental Science and Mathematics. The teachers are assisting by the ERC in curriculum plan and preparation. These Primaries were activated as feeders for Pudami Neighborhood schools.

(vi) Education Resource Centre

DRF's education resource centre looks after the pedagogical and academic requirements of neighborhood schools. It also undertakes research on a variety of aspects of schooling and education. In association with government, civil society organization and individuals working in the field of child rights and education, the ERC shares and generates resources between partners.

(vii) Spreading the Neighbourhood School plan

In the year 2007, DRF organized a national conference on Neighborhood Schools at Hyderabad. Focus by representatives from academia, bureaucracy, NGOs and the private industries, the conference discussed the idea of neighborhood schools that would assure access to quality education for children from various sections of society. It was necessary to encourage the plan of place up neighborhood schools on public private partnership (PPPs).

(c) Health Education, DRFHE

Dr. Reddy's center purpose and inclusive education is its means of between with society and corporate, DRFHE is a perfect fusion of the two as long as health care education to professionals who can help the medical organization to create more integrative healthcare services. It as well speaks to the gap in patient awareness, enable them with self care skill and improving the cost effectiveness of syndrome management. While 2003, DRFHE's 1 year post-graduate course in management of health care has

situated 212 pupils in pharma companies, hospitals and clinics. Physiotherapy, dentistry, nutrition pharmacy, hospital administration and biosciences are a little of the subjects. The graduates employment as educators, counselors, physician's assistants and associates. Beyond the previous year, Sparsh has afforded excellence and convincingly priced anticancer medicines to above 500 patients, throughout the doctors. 200 patients suffer from non-hodgkin's lymphoma benefit from our new drug reditux TM, which was launched previous year.

(i) Helping Doctors

At the point of doctors the domestic circle series help out doctors to build up extra-medical soft aptitude and companies competencies to be more flourishing in their competent careers.

(ii) Enabling Patients life at your doorstep

Company's health education introduces two continuing education activities in the previous year. Continuation at your entry a soothing care plan is focused on as long as reprieve to continually and incurably ill patients throughout indication and ache administration and by counseling the family members.

(iii) Art of Living Foundation and DRFHE

DRFHE, in conjunction with art of living foundation (AOL) launched a pilot way of life corporate program. This deal supports and helps affliction patients from chronic disease to adopt way of life modify to reduce risk issues and to self-manage their condition. Ten metabolic disease patient's advantage from the first 7 day program.

(iv) Sparsh

Dr. Reddy's patient assistance program continues to improve the convenience of oncology drugs to diseased patients in requirement. More the previous phase, sparsh has provide good quality and discounted priced anti-cancer medicines toward 500 patients, throughout the doctors treatment. Almost 200 patients undergoing from non-hodgkin's lymphoma accomplished from our inventive drug Reditux TM.

(B) Cairn India Ltd

The CSR initiatives of the Cairn India was focused towards 8 wide themes with objectives to improve generally socio-economic pointers of companies area of function: (a) Promoting healthcare, (b) sanitation and making safe drinking water available; (c) Promoting education and sports; (d) Employment enhancement through training and vocational skill development; (e) Income enhancement through farm based and other livelihood opportunities; (f) Ensuring Sustainable environment; (g) Rural Development Projects; (h) Rural development projects.

(a) Preventive health care

Company providing mobile health van facilities for the rural remote population. Cairn India's area of function was to give access to doubtful health care. 250,000 citizens advantaged from this programs each year. Course carries out throughout local government and NGO partners under national level rural health mission schemes. The 5 year programs in association with local government and NGO associates to recover health care services. This programs aims to decrease control of prevalent illness, child and maternal transience and get better primary healthcare access.

(b) Safe drinking water and Sanitation

Company providing access to sanitation facilities to rural remote households in partnership along with locally Panchayat. All panchayat areas to be covered over the next 3 years. Providing safe drinking water amenities for the remote rural population in company's functional vicinity by location up water kiosks using RO technology. The effective programs were extended during 2014-2015 to new villages on requirement basis and would be executed through NGO partnership.

(c) Promoting sports and education

Companies 3 year programs in association with state government and NGO partnership, to develop quality of education and sports in larger than fifty remote rural Government primary and high

schools. Programs aims to improve educational enrolment, performance, decrease in drop-out rate and gender gap.

(d) Employment enhancing job skills

Employment connected professional skills training with plan to train and employ over 4000 people in the remote rural areas in excess of the next 5 years. Teaching was executed by multi super specialized training sources. Cairn Center was built-up by the company in Jodhpur to give advance occupational skillfulness trainings on a variety of industrial section. The centre is probable to start in second half of 2014-2015 with plan to coach and employ larger than 3,000 rural people in the subsequently 5 years and training was provided by specialized training partnership.

(e) Livelihood and Income Enhancement

Increase sustainable community and increase income of livelihood through irrigate harvesting and improved performance in farming, livestock and produce market associations. It was expected to increase income of over 20,000 farmers in Cairn's operational vicinity over the next 5 years and program will be executed through NGO partners.

(f) Sustainable environment

Increase green belt area coverage in the local and near areas of company's function for sustainable environment. The programs was carried out in joint venture with local panchayat, forest department and the NGO partner.

(g) Rural Development Projects

To undertaken community requirement based projects that get better quality of life in rural areas by setting up quality health and education facilities. Company provided access to electricity to households of rural areas through solar PV based projects in joint venture with Government. Small group community requirement based projects in remote rural areas to promote locally community development.

Conclusion

While, there are adequate laws and regulations which focus on social responsibility of the corporate in the direction of ensuring a further harmonious balanced and developmental approach of welfare orientation. Although, there has been less success in accomplishing the corporate social responsibility goals. Specified the uncertain scenario of economic development joined with pervasive unemployment and poverty, it turn into extremely complicated on the government part to take severe initiatives adjacent to domestic and international company to make sure better fulfillment to laws and regulations of CSR. Relatively, minor labour standards and environmental of FDIs aims are attractive to international company, since such indulgence make better production effectiveness with enhance competitiveness within the short period, consequential into productivity along with maximized profits. This is reason of the most important reasons for indifference to powerfully compulsory laws and regulations associated to Indian corporate social responsibility. It has uniformly accurate that the associations among a variety of company stakeholders are appropriate more interdependent, responsible, harmonious and transparent (Herrman, 2004).

Indian companies have the most excellent rankings of CSR in the globe with a few of the Indian private sector companies have evenly earned admire for their struggles in the area of health, education along with schemes of welfare orientation. Large schemes of welfare similar to countrywide food security Act require vigorous financial supports needs from company to construct such systems for the Inclusive development of the country success. Civil society, NGOs with media contain additional improved the capacity for better harmony as well as co-operation among the society and company in they operate. Ultimately, we have a democracy of society welfare orientation in which our political lessons must be responsive headed for the welfare of the each and every citizen.

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